

Determinants of Fundamental Stock Return Factors at Mining Company; Analysis Data Panel for Period 2012 - 2017

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Abstract:

This research aims to examine and analyze the effect of return on assets, debt to equity ratio, dividend payout ratio, exchange rates and world oil prices on the value of the stock of mining companies in the Indonesia Stock Exchange for the period of 2012 to 2017. This research uses annual data for the observation period from 2012 to 2017. The population is mining companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2012 to 2017 and up to 32 companies. The sampling technique used purposive sampling, found a sample of 32 companies with 6 years observation so that the total observation obtained was 192. The model used is the Common Effect Model. The results of the analysis show that the exchange rates and world oil prices have a significant positive effect, while the return on assets, debt to equity ratio, dividend payout ratio have no significant effect on stock returns of mining companies in the Indonesia Stock Exchange for the period of 2012 to 2017.

Keywords: Return On Asset, Debt To Equity Ratio, Dividend Payout Ratio, Exchange Rates, World Oil Prices, Stock Returns.

1. Introduction

Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) is the current capital market Transaction Center. Indonesia Stock Exchange as one of the capital market that can be used as alternative funding for all sectors of the company in Indonesia. One of the funding alternatives is through the issuance and sale of stocks on the stock exchange (Benyamin and Endri, 2019). Sectors in the Indonesia Stock Exchange are the mining sector. There are 42 companies in the mining sector. The subsectors referred to are coal subsectors, oil and gas, metals and other minerals and rocks. The mining sector has an important role as the provider of energy resources needed for a country's economic growth, as the mining sector is a natural resource that can be used in power plants. The mining sector has a major contribution to various aspects ranging from foreign investment (PMA), domestic investment (PMDN), export activities, foreign exchange receipts, state revenues, and gross domestic products. The mining sector is also able to open the job field and absorb the workforce which later reduce unemployment and require large funds so as to fulfill the funds the company will need funds from investors, hence the author is interested in researching mining sector companies in hopes of providing better information for other authors and prospective investors who want to invest in stocks (Widyawati and Endri, 2018). Here is the sector price index data that is in the IDX period 2012-2017.

Picture 1

Sectoral Stock Price Index in IDX

Moreover, interestingly, the relation of the index movement of the mining sector with the current JCI gradually began to strengthen again. Based on Bareska's data release on 17 October 2016, the correlation value of the mining sector's movement to the IDX in the early February period until last weekend increased to 91 percent. The second correlation value until the end of June 2016 is still around 67.26 percent. The more powerful the correlation of the mining sector Index movement with IDX showed that the mining sector index movement began to push the rates of IDX. It is not impossible that mining stocks will again support the rate of IDX if the correlation continues to increase. It has occurred in the period of June 2006-February 2008 then, when the mining sector stocks experienced a significant increase as the oil price increases in the world.

Based on Bareksa's data, the mining sector's stocks have increased five-fold in that period. The increase in stocks of the mining sector led to the promotion of the composite Stock Price Index (JCI) to the 2,734 level in 2008 from 1,287 in 2006. The movement of the mining sector stocks during this time greatly affects the rates of movement. Because the value of correlation with the mining sector to reach 93.45 percent which means that the mining sector greatly affects the rates of the IDX movement. At that time, mining stocks such as PT Bumi Resources TBK (BUMI) even became a prima investor.

To assess the company's financial, the company usually uses the ratio analysis of financial statements or better known by the traditional approach. But this approach has some disadvantages that do not take into account the cost of capital and there are differences in the implementation of accounting practices among companies. The financial ratio can only assess the liquidity, profitability, efficiency, and leverage alone, not able to measure the financial performance of the company's value (Daeli nad Endri, 2018). So the financial ratios make it difficult to determine whether a company has managed to create value or not. In addition to other macroeconomic factors that need to be considered are the rates and prices of the crude oil throughout the world.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Signaling Theory

Signaling Theory or signal theory was developed by Ross (1977). The theory states that the company's executives have better information about their company and will be encouraged to deliver the information to prospective investors to increase the price of the company's shares. Cues or signals are an action that a company takes to instruct investors on how management views the company's prospects.

2.2 Asset Pricing Model

Asset pricing theories postulate that differences in expected returns are related to the covariances of securities with marginal utility. The marginal utility may depend on several economic risk factors, in which case several "betas" may be required to measure risk. Firm-specific attributes have traditionally served as alternatives to beta in tests of these asset pricing models. For example, the firm "size-effect" first drew attention as a challenge to the CAPM. The literature continued in this tradition with the ratios of stock market price to earnings and the book value of equity (e.g. Basu, 1977; Chan et al., 1991; Fama and French, 1992). The evidence of these studies suggests that such firm-specific attributes are important for explaining equity returns in the United States and Japan. Ferson and Harvey (1994), find that similar variables are important at the country level.

2.3 Stock Returns

Stock return can be defined as a level of profit obtained and expected by investors from an investment for a certain period of time that will be obtained in the future. Return is the profit obtained by companies, individuals and institutions from the results of the investment policies that they do (Benyamin and Endri, 2019). According to Endri (2018), one of the factors that motivate investors to invest in return. Return is the result obtained from investment activities

2.4. Return On Assets

According to Prastowo (2002:86), Return on Assets (ROA) is used to measure the effectiveness of the company in generating profits by exploiting its assets. This ratio may give an indication of good or bad neighbor management in implementing cost control or management of his property. Return on Assets (ROA) is often used as a tool to measure the rate of return on total assets after interest expense and taxes, (Endri 2012). The high Return On Assets (ROA) will be good for the company.

2.5. Leverage

Bhandari (1988) finds that firms with high leverage (high debt/equity ratios) have higher average returns than firms with low leverage for the 1948-1979 period. This result persists after size and beta are included as explanatory variables. High leverage increases the riskiness of a firm's equity, but this increased risk should be reflected in a higher beta coefficient. Consequently, Bhandari's results are yet another deviation from the CAPM predictions

2.6. Dividend Payout Ratio

Pandey (2015) stated firmly that dividend Policy is a decision by the financial manager whether the firm should distribute all profit or retain them or to distribute a portion and retain the balance. Moreover, it has been discovered that the dividend policy of a firm always has a short term or long term effect on the market price of its shares. It is quite difficult to clearly identify the effects of payout on firm's valuation since the valuation of a firm is a reflection of so many factors such that the long run effect of payout is quite difficult to separate.

2.7. Exchange Rates

Exchange rate volatility is a real challenge for investors in investing the money in the capital market because the fluctuating exchange rate is a very basic statistics for investors in carrying out the economic activities (Kurniadi, 2013). The depreciated Rupiah exchange rate will result in greater costs to be borne by the company and reduces the level of profitability, especially for companies that rely solely on raw materials from abroad, and will also be able to hit companies that only rely on foreign loans in the form of US dollars to finance their operations. This will reduce the company's stock price traded on the capital market. Fluctuations in the value of the Rupiah towards a stable foreign currency will greatly affect the investment climate in the country, especially the capital market. The appreciation of the Rupiah exchange rate toward the dollar will have an impact on the development of the marketing of Indonesian products abroad, especially in terms of price competition. If this happens, it will indirectly have an effect on the trade balance, because of the decrease in the import value compared with the export value. Furthermore, it will also affect Indonesia's balance of payments, which increases due to greater exports than imports, which in turn has a positive impact on the stock market (Kurniadi, 2013)

2.8. World Oil Prices

The movement of world crude oil prices also affects the movement of the stock price of mining companies. The world oil price used in this research is the price of West Texas Intermediate (WTI) or light sweet. World oil price is an indicator of the world economy because crude oil is needed for the economic activity. This is because capital market investors consider that increasing demand indicates the improvement in the global economy after the crisis. According to IMF in Khin and Thambiah (2015), "the high price of crude petroleum oil continued to be an issue of concern all over the world and it had also a major impact on almost all emerging countries." An increase in world oil demand was followed by increasing demand for mining commodities. Conversely, falling energy prices reflect a weakening of the global economic recovery. Therefore, if oil prices increase, expectations for the improved performance of companies will also increase and automatically the stock price will increase (Jatiroso, 2014; Hasyim and Jabid, 2019)

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research methods and variables

The method that used in this research is an associative method. The associative method is a research aimed at determining the influence or also the relationship between two or more variables. This research aims to test the relationship between independent variables (free), namely *Return On Asset*, *Debt To Equity Ratio*, *Dividend Payout Ratio*, *Exchange Rates* and world oil prices to Stock Returns as dependent variable (bound).

3.2. Analysis tools and regression models

In analyzing this research author using the E-Views vers tool. 9.0. or higher. The data analysis methods in this research used the Data Panel regression analysis approach. The Data regression analysis Panel is used to examine the hypotheses that have been filed in the research. The Data panel is a combination of *cross-section* and *time series*. The data regression Model of the panel can be formulated as follows :

$$\text{Return} = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{ROA}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{DER}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{DPR}_{it} + \beta_4 \text{Rates}_{it} + \beta_5 \text{Oil Price};$$

$$i = 1, 2, \dots, N; \quad t = 1, 2, \dots, T$$

Description:

Return	= Stock Returns
ROA	= Return on Assets
DER	= Debt To Equity Ratio
DPR	= Dividend Payout Ratio
Rates	= Exchange rate
Oil price	= Oil prices
α	= Constants
β	= regression coefficient
E	= residual error

4. RESULTS OF RESEARCH AND EXPLANATION

4.1. Descriptive Data

Descriptive statistics are intended to provide an overview or explanation of the data of a variable that is researched, variables used include, return on asset, debt to equity ratio, dividend payout ratio, exchange rates and oil price to stock

Returns. From the results of descriptive statistical analysis to the six variables with the research sample (n = 192), and the results have been depicted on the table below.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistical Analysis Results

	RETURN	ROA	DER	DPR	KURS	OIL_PRICE
Mean	0.082965	0.550625	1.477135	10.39953	0.073118	-0.041946
Median	-0.014563	1.730000	0.785000	0.000000	0.043490	0.001318
Maximum	7.595749	38.00000	28.19000	126.7300	0.260496	0.397419
Minimum	-1.811959	-72.13000	-24.12000	0.000000	-0.026024	-0.392707
Std. Dev.	0.865052	13.03656	4.220259	21.89612	0.094429	0.282880
Skewness	3.734824	-2.580480	1.419341	2.520363	1.043999	0.092983
Kurtosis	31.80334	15.47145	23.63869	9.621456	2.872699	1.723613
Jarque-Bera	7083.424	1457.380	3472.110	554.0207	35.00751	13.30998
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.001288
Sum	15.92924	105.7200	283.6100	1996.710	14.03874	-8.053660
Sum Sq. Dev.	142.9282	32460.81	3401.822	91573.04	1.703128	15.28401
Observations	192	192	192	192	192	192

Source: Data processing result with Eviews version 9.0, (2018).

1. The stock return variable shows a minimum value of -1.811959 and a maximum value of 7.595749 and the company average has a stock return value of 0.082965 with a standard deviation of 0.865052. Can be seen in the variable return stock, the standard deviation value is always greater than the mean can be concluded that there is a large fluctuation of the variable stock returns against the mining companies in the IDX.
2. The return on asset variable shows a minimum value of -72.13000 and a maximum value of 38 and the company average has a return on the asset value of 0.550625 with a standard deviation of 13.04829. The mean value of the deviation standard looks smaller, indicating that there are no substantial fluctuations of the ROA variable against the mining companies in the IDX.
3. The variable debt to equity ratio shows a minimum value of -24.12000 and a maximum value of 28.19000 and the company average has a debt to equity ratio of 1.477135 with a standard deviation of 4.220259. For the mean value of the standard deviation is smaller, indicating that there are no substantial fluctuations of the DER variables against mining companies in the IDX.
4. The dividend payout ratio variable shows a minimum value of 0 and a maximum value of 126.7300 and the average company has a dividend payout ratio of 10.39953 with a standard deviation of 21.89612. The default value of the deviation looks larger than the mean value indicating that there is a large fluctuation of the DPR variable against the mining companies in the IDX.
5. The exchange rate is the amount of money from a particular currency that can be exchanged with one currency unit of another country, which in this case the Rupiah against the US dollar. Exchange rates variables show a minimum value of -0.026024 and a maximum value of 0.260496 and the company average has an exchange rates value of 0.073118 with a standard deviation of 0.094429. The default value of the deviation looks larger than the mean value indicating that there is a large fluctuation of the rate variable against the mining companies in the IDX.
6. Oil prices, in this case, are on the price of West Texas Intermediate (WTI) which is a price standard widely used in measuring the oil prices of the world. The oil price variable shows a minimum value of -0.392707 and a maximum value of 0.397419 and the average company has a value of oil priced at -0.041946 with a standard deviation of 0.282880.

4.2. Data Regression Analysis Panel

Table 2 Conclusion Testing Model Data Regression Panel

No	Method	p-value ($\alpha=0,05$)	Result
1	Chow-Test	0.8638	Common Effect
2	Lagrange Multiplier-BP	0.2188	Common Effect
3	Hausman Test	1.0000	Random Effect

The data regression analysis of the panels used in the hypothesis testing is to test the effect of *return on asset*, *debt to equity ratio*, *dividend payout ratio*, exchange rates, and world oil prices on stock returns. From the two previous tests, namely the *Chow Test* and the *LM Breusch-Pagan (BP)*, it was concluded that the authors' data would be more appropriate using the *Common Effect Model (CEM)*. Here is an *Eviews output* for the data regression panel using the *Common Effect Model (CEM)*.

Table 3 Panel Data Regression Analysis Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	T-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.250042	0.082923	3.015363	0.0029
ROA	0.007770	0.004975	1.561704	0.1201
DER	-0.007724	0.014222	-0.543107	0.5877
DPR	0.000674	0.002945	0.228916	0.8192
KURS	-1.921199	0.640319	-3.000379	0.0031
OIL_PRICE	0.631316	0.215652	2.927475	0.0038
F-statistic	5.115083	Durbin-Watson stat		1.809714
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000203			
R-squared	0.120881			
Adjusted R-squared	0.097249			

Source: Data processing results with Eviews version 9.0, (2018)

Impact of return on the asset on stock returns

The results of this research were not in line with the previous research conducted by Endri (2018), and Putra (2016) stating that ROA had a *significant* influence on the stock returns. The first hypothesis (H_1) states that the *return on asset* value does not affect the return of the stock, received. This indicates that the return on the asset has no significant effect on the stock returns. *Return on assets (ROA)* is a ratio that shows how much the company's assets are used effectively to generate profits. While stock returns are the value of shares in Rupiah formed due to the action of buying and selling of stock on stock exchanges by fellow exchange members. The bigger the ROA shows the better the performance, because of the greater the rate of *return*. ROA also reflects greater gains in profits. Increasing profits cause investors to invest more in the stock of a company, and therefore profits can affect the stock returns. In the results of the ROA research show no effect on the company's stock *returns*, this is because the ROA ratio only shows the company's ability to generate profit with the investment of the owner, but lacking the ability to forecast future prospects, therefore investors are less willing to place their investments into the company. Since ROA is less of a concern to investors in making investments and therefore, utilization of ROA as a forecasting tool for investors does not affect the *return* of the company's stock price.

Impact of debt to equity ratio on the stock returns

The second hypothesis (H_2) states that the *debt to equity ratio* does not affect stock returns, is accepted. This indicates that the value of debt to equity ratio has no significant effect on the value of the stock. DER does not affect the stock returns because DER is the ratio of leverage describing the risk level of a company due to debt usage for its operations. It is incompatible with the research results of AL-Qudah and Laham (2013), Sari (2017) indicating that DER negatively affects the stock *returns*. From the results of the research, it can be concluded that an investor does not purchase shares based upon or focused on the DER value of a company but upon another values and factors, they deem more pertinent toward determining positive stock returns. The results of this research in line with the previous research conducted by Gharaibeth (2014) said DER was influential but not significant to the stock returns, and Sari (2017) said DER had no significant influence on stock returns. Another research from Khairani, et al. (2014) said DER had a positive influence on stock returns.

Impact of dividend payout ratio on stock returns

The third hypothesis (H_3) states that the dividend payout ratio (DPR) does not affect the value of stocks. This means that the dividend payout ratio has no significant effect on the stock returns. Therefore, larger dividend payments made by a company will reduce the company's ability to invest, so that will lower the company's growth rate, which will further lower the stock price in the future. The decrease in stock price will result in declining stock value of the company. It is not following the hypotheses previously created. Investors prefer to receive high capital gains compared to dividends as they can delay tax payments. Moreover, investors prefer capital gains because dividends tend to be taxed higher than capital gains. So a company is better off to establish a low dividend payout ratio to minimize the cost of capital and maximize return to the company. Thereby, the dividends policy can

negatively affect the stock returns. The impact of DPR on stock value has been analyzed in studies by Sari (2017) and Puspitasari and Purnamasari (2013) which concluded the DPR has no significant influence on the stock returns. Another research from Ahmed (2014) said the DPR has a positive influence on the stock returns.

Impact of the exchange rates against stock returns

The fourth hypothesis (H_4), which states that the exchange rate (rates) affect the *return* of the stock, is accepted, indicating that the exchange rates significantly affect the stock *returns*. This hypothesis concludes that the higher valued rupiah against other world currencies will impact the rising price of the stock. The results of this research in line with the research conducted by Eva (2014) said the exchange rate has a positive influence on the stock returns. However, contrary to this is the research conducted by Widya (2015) which stated the exchange rates has no significant effect on the stock returns. The exchange rates of the rupiah have a positive influence on the economy and capital markets in Indonesia. The weakening exchange rates of rupiah against foreign currency results in the inclusion of foreign investors because when the exchange rates weaken, Bank Indonesia will raise the interest rate so that foreign investors will be more interested to invest in the form of deposits or savings that will lead to increased stock prices.

Impact of world oil prices on stock returns

The research results of the fifth hypothesis (H_5) which states that world oil prices affect stock returns. This research is in line with the research of Gupta (2016) saying world oil prices have a significant positive effect on stock returns. Other studies from Hanafiah (2015) are not in line with this position and counter that world oil prices did not have a significant effect on stock returns. World oil prices are influential because the government has revoked subsidies on fuel oil energy source in the production of the mining sector, additionally, the price of domestic oil is fully determined by the government.

Impact of return on assets, debt to equity ratio, dividend payout ratio, exchange rate, and world oil prices affect stock returns

The results of the research of the sixth hypothesis (H_6) which states that return on assets, debt to equity ratio, dividend payout ratio, exchange rates, and world oil prices affect the stock returns received. The results of this research support the results of previous studies stating that return on assets, debt to equity ratio, dividend payout ratio, exchange rates, and world oil prices affect stock value.

5. Conclusion

1. There is no significant influence from return on the asset on stock returns. This may be because industrial companies in this research are affected by the impact of the global crises which decrease the availability of equity to these companies to make investments. Because of the higher the ROA ratio, the better the state of the company.
2. There is no significant influence on debt to equity ratio on stock returns. There is a belief amounts investors that the use of debt can result in future losses for a company and the level of return to investors will also decline.
3. There is no significant influence on the dividend payout ratio on stock returns, the greater the dividend payment made to investors reduces the company's ability to invest, so that lowers the growth rate of the company, which further lowers the stock price. The stock price drop will result in declining stock returns.
4. There is a significant influence of the exchange rates on the stock returns, meaning that an increase in exchange rates will cause an increase in the value of the stock.
5. There is a significant influence on the price of world oil on stock returns, meaning the higher the price of the world oil then the value of stocks will be increased.
6. There is a significant influence on stock returns when one simultaneously considers the return on asset, debt to equity ratio, dividend payout ratio, exchange rates and oil prices of the world. Meaning that when a company is impacted positively by each of these factors that may increase stock value, the stock returns to the investor will increase as well.

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